

MODERN APPROACHES OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' CREATIVE THINKING SKILLS

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Annotation: This article investigates the modern approaches of developing students' creative thinking skills in a modern educational environment, and gives recommendations about organizing an effective teaching process.

Key words: creative thinking, attitude, mindset, opinion, process, approach, teacher, knowledge, upbringing.

Today, the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan, which are consistently implemented in our country, have determined a new stage of development. The practical results, signs and characteristics of this process are evident in all aspects of our life today, most importantly, in the consciousness, aspirations and actions of our people. We can say that the Action strategy plays a fundamental role in the scientific-theoretical, practical and constructive basis of rapid development of Uzbekistan, and it is a program that is adopted to the new era of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the basis of this state program, it can be recognized that practical work on the formation of a comprehensive continuous education system, which includes the process of educating the young generation with in-depth knowledge and thorough professional training at the levels from preschool education to higher education, is being continued more consistently.

Currently, increasing the competitiveness of future teachers, developing the number of creative people in society, training creative personnel are considered the most crucial issues. Because we can say that young people who have developed creative thinking and independent opinions make a great contribution to the further development of society through their confidence in their knowledge and personal opinions.

Comprehension and thinking are forms of creative activity, which are developed by training abilities. When we talk about creative thinking, we mean a complex mental process. Creative thinking encourages students to think creatively. Creative thinking is a complex process in which students are encouraged to think creatively, and they are guided to creativity and independent thinking.

Through creative thinking, students can:

- learn independently and consciously;
- always move forward;
- reasonable resolution of various conflicting and problematic situations;
- be taught unconventional and new thinking.

In this case, students analyze information from simple to complex and vice versa, from complex to simple situations. Another way to develop students' creative thinking is to create conditions for free thinking in classes. It will be effective if students discuss the literature they have read so that they can think freely in the lessons. In this, students try to express their opinions about the work, give critical comments to the opinions of their peers, and justify their opinions. Usually, such classes give students the opportunity to listen and communicate, discuss controversial issues, think creatively and increase their ability to think creatively, and strengthen their ability to form their own opinion. In this case, it is appropriate for the teacher to use methods and methods that encourage the formation of students' creative thinking in the lessons.

The conditions and requirements of problem-based education are also characterized by the fact that they focus on creative thinking and creative attitude. Below we will focus on an innovative approach aimed at developing students' creative relational thinking.

Today, in our country, great attention is being paid to training highly qualified, competitive specialists by educating young people who are independent and creative thinkers, have a high passion for creativity. It is known to us that in all periods, the content of the educational system has developed in accordance with social development. Even in today's digital educational environment, future teachers need to master the disciplines of pedagogy and psychology in order to develop their aptitude, ability, knowledge and skills to meet the requirements of the times, and to acquire the chosen pedagogical profession at the level of demand.

In this process, it is desirable for them to make full use of all opportunities to organize independent and creative work effectively. Because for the development of our country, we need specialists with developed thinking who can enter into a wide-ranging creative attitude, who can think independently. Teaching future teachers to independent creative thinking and attitude is the need of the hour. Because tomorrow's children should be able to think independently and creatively throughout their lives, at all stages of education. And it depends on the future teachers of today.

It is desirable for future teachers to focus on one thing at a time. Accelerated flow of information enters the social processes, they should be able to receive, analyze, process, conclude information very quickly and, most importantly, convey their content to the young students, relying on reasonable, scientific sources. For this, the implementation of pedagogical technology in the educational process will serve to positively solve the above-mentioned current problem.

In the modern interpretation, it is appropriate for the pedagogue's activity to acquire an innovative character in accordance with the modern educational

environment. V.A. Slastenin [1] considers innovation to be a set of purposeful, directed processes aimed at creating, spreading and using new things. According to him, any innovation aims to satisfy the needs of subjects and stimulate their aspirations with the help of new tools.

R.N. Yusufbekova [2] considers pedagogical innovations as aspirations that lead to previously unknown, unobserved, unrecorded conditions or results in educational processes. A. I. Prigozhin [3] tried to illuminate two micro levels of the innovation process. Well-known scientist N.A. Muslimov [4] tried to justify the systematic concept of innovation in his research.

An innovative approach to the formation of the thinking of creative relations in future teachers is determined by the following:

- creativity;
- creative qualities;
- willingness to learn new things;
- assimilation of pedagogical innovations and creative approach to it;
- innovation;
- communicativeness.

Innovative activities aimed at forming the thinking of creative relations in future teachers should mainly focus on the psychological, physiological and intellectual actions of students. In this process, as a result of working on themselves, they acquire thinking skills and competences related to creative attitude, and they approach pedagogical activities creatively.

Pedagogical innovative activity aimed at forming the thinking of creative relations in future teachers is manifested on the basis of the following signs. These are:

- the desire to acquire knowledge about the thinking of creative relations;
- mastering creative pedagogical research methods;
- ability to create author's concepts;

- ability to cooperate;
- being able to provide methodical support for creative exchange of ideas and cooperation;
- ability to resolve pedagogical conflicts;
- creative approach to news, such as adapting them to pedagogical activities.

It would be efficient if teachers could implement above mentioned techniques in their teaching process.

To conclude, we can say that in order to develop future teachers' creative thinking abilities we must create all necessary conditions and facilities in educational institutions.

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